

CYBORGS AND RESISTANCE: DISSOLUTION OF HUMAN IN ARAFAT MAZHAR'S SHEHR-E-TABASSUM AND DAVID JAMES ARMSBY'S MODEL CITIZEN

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Abstract

This research examines the salient features of dystopian fiction through Foucault's concept of panopticon in animated short films. The aim is to conduct a comparative analysis of Arafat Mazhar's 'Shehr-e-Tabassum' (2020) and David James Armsby's 'Model Citizen' (2020) by analysing animations of futuristic metropolitan spaces as foundations of control. The objective is to reveal how both the films under discussion build on narratives which mirror contemporary, claustrophobic societal structures, while criticizing the dissolution and reduction of individuals of society into artificially driven cyborgs. Conducting a qualitative study of dystopian societies presented in digital media animations, this research investigates how visualisation uniquely captures and communicates the prevalence of surveillance at state level. It also tends to showcase unchallengeable power dynamics inherent in modern so-called democratic societies. The research challenges the normalization of surveillance and internalized discipline using color scheme, characters, masks, camera angles and perspective. It highlights the perspective of Pakistani and Scottish directors from an omnipresent observer's point of view, while focusing on selected animated films from East and West situating their commonalities. The paper tends to explore how visual narrative, artistic representation, and adaptations enhance our understanding of the 'panopticon' and its implications. Moreover, it also discusses the role of animation in shaping and influencing cultural perceptions, changing belief systems and fostering critical discourse on surveillance, control, and individual freedom of modern-day citizens. This research contributes to the growing scholarship on dystopian animation studies, and Foucault's concept of panopticon. It attempts to demonstrate resistance as an antidote to totalitarian control while contextualizing the argument in a global scenario.

INTRODUCTION

Dystopia in the twenty-first century has been one of the most popular themes in contemporary literary forms depicting the prevalent claustrophobic societal structures. Interestingly, the emerging streaks of artificial intelligence's role in the dissolution of human individuality have been explored at length in

digital media such as films especially, across the borders. The pre-occupation of authors, artists and researchers with the nightmarish and anti-utopian vision of the world is a mutual concern. In a time and age, where control and surveillance have taken precedence over gradually fading humanity, the

current era has been witnessing an ever-increasing obsession with apocalyptic and post-apocalyptic narratives. Agency has been utilized as a tool, to criticise and highlight dystopian societies at a global level. It tends to challenge and ultimately subvert the unchallengeable power dynamics at play. The future implications of failing to uphold and materialise democratic spirit in nations is reflected in the animations which are under discussion in this research. The futuristic metropolitan spaces act as frameworks of control. They have been crucial in shaping and influencing cultural perceptions.

Hence, these visual narratives become a major foundation for informing the audience about the threat to individuality through dominance of uniformity. These animations enable people to see through the reality of modern society which still lacks the acceptance of diversity. Therefore, dystopian fiction attempts to historicise the critical discourse on surveillance, control, individual freedom and humanism in the twentieth and twenty-first century. This discussion is based on two animated short films Arafat Mazhar's 'Shehr-e-Tabassum' (2020) and David James Armsby's 'Model Citizen' (2020). These films build on the observations and fictional accounts of so-called, modern democratic societies by Pakistani and Scottish directors. The comparison and contrast of East versus West, whilst maintaining intersection of themes has been explored through various cinematic techniques employed by both Mazhar and Armsby. Model Citizen (2020) by David James Armsby criticizes the rise of perfectionism and uniformity in society. The short film is black and white, a fictional account of society dulled and overcome by surveillance. It is set in a fully automated town named AutoDale. The film is an attempt by the Scottish director to reveal the dangers of subduing to societal expectations. It showcases the bleak consequences of submission resulting in the erasure of identity and diversity in humans. Released on 10th September 2020 in English and Spanish, the film has received an overall rating of 6.5/10 on IMDB. The storyline revolves around the idea of a dystopian world where everyone is born and raised to become a model citizen. On the other hand, Shehr-e-Tabassum (2020) by Arafat Mazhar captures the society where masses are monitored continuously through security bots. The animated short film is full of neon colors against black

backdrop, presenting a strikingly, chaotic society. Citizens are continuously instructed to wear their 'smileton'. People are only allowed to smile, expressions other than smile are against the established law. Thus, the short film is an attempt to reveal the havoc of technology in the futuristic world. Michel Foucault's (1975) Discipline and Punish: The Birth of Prison, explores the eerie concept of the ever-watching eyes, that is, panopticon. This term is influenced by Jeremy Bentham's architectural structure. Panopticon is of primary importance in understanding the role of power structures controlling and establishing conformity in society. Therefore, it is applied to critically analyse the dystopia in Shehr-e Tabassum and Model Citizen.

Literature Review

Understanding dystopian fiction is an integral aspect in making sense of the discrepancies of the governing social and political systems. In an era where surveillance and control are made use of to regulate the societies, Foucault's (1975) notion of panopticon gains relevance. In Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison by Michel Foucault (1975), the famous French philosopher elaborates on the prevalence of restrictive environment in modern societies. Amidst the debates revolving around an individual's right to freedom of speech and choices, the facade of democracy, inclusive environment and acceptance of diversity is debunked.

Foucault's (1975) concept of panopticon has been observed as a primary tool which is used for exercising social control in communities. It operates through a mechanism of self-regulation. According to Moylas, these narratives are focused on "more pervasive [and less visible] tyranny of cooperation." (2003,135) Being a citizen of a society that is governed by surveillance, the individuals are pushed to work on their behaviour and actions to conform to the societal norms. Such is the power of control ingrained in the citizens, that they remain subservient even when there is no evident law and enforcement to discipline them. Foucault expands on the inculcation of numerous ideological state apparatuses undertaken to achieve complete subjugation of the subjects. Involuntary sterilization by racist, colonialist or authoritarian states is intended to reform the behaviour of mass populations rather than targeting an individual alone.

Dystopian fiction provides a disclaimer to its audience highlighting the after-effects of totalitarianism and complete subjugation to the societal norms and political laws for an average citizen. In recent times, the dependence on artificial intelligence is experiencing a boom. Inclination of societies and its policy makers, towards implementation of rigid law enforcement is criticized, before it becomes completely destructive. It is not just state power, but also the amalgamation of modern technology in the structure and strictures of the society that holds the possibility of turning it into a grim experience for the populace. Mahida (2014) in "Dystopian Future in Contemporary Science Fiction" writes about the destructive use of technology as, "Much of their literature contained visions of the apocalyptic end of the world at the hands of men with technology". Thus, dystopian fiction warns about the abuses of technology affecting human survival.

Panopticon proposes that the emerging trend of state authorities aims at neutralising the rational beings. Ultimately, causing an erasure of collective histories and memories in a dystopian society; these elements are becoming more critical in nature. Biotechnologies and cyborgs are experiencing an increased participation in contemporary societies run by corporate powers. Therefore, the impact that technological advancements are having on humanity cannot be undermined. These are bringing about major flux in societies. "Thus, emerging technology has the power to affect our lives, and implement changes to our body, mind and soul" (Kolko, 2010). Apart from these, it has also cast its shadow on the way humans had previously perceived the world around them and their own self.

Presence of cyborg in fiction is questionable. It raises the concern about human existence. Contemporary sci-fi includes a lot of cyborg elements to narrate the inclusion of technology in the human body. David Dalton (2023) in "Reactionary, Robo-Sacer Dystopias: Cyborg Oppression and Right-Wing Bio politics in Francisco Laresgoiti's 2033," describes about the use of technology for oppressing state citizens. The eye drop altogether changes the perceptions of human beings in the film, "2033". Dystopia in the film possess the progressive members of the society as a threat to the prevailing law and order (Dalton, 2023). Such merging of the technology in the human body,

as presented in dystopian fiction, raise fear among the readers: of an external source hijacking their cognitive abilities.

Dystopian fiction presents a world that is under the control of an authoritarian regime due to the use of surveillance techniques. Margret Atwood's novel offer such world where apparently, the autocrats have created a stability, and the need for the resistance reduces significantly. Angela Leflan (2009) in, "There's a Shock in This Seeing": The Problem of the Image in *The Handmaid's Tale* and *Oryx and Crake*," writes about such societies as "this appearance of control and stability is ultimately designed to maintain the status quo." (105) The power emanates through the structures of control.

Dystopian fiction is an evolving genre. From representation of moral destruction of society, to the synthesis of misuse of technology, dystopian fiction as a genre, is also adapting to the various trends. Dystopia in literary and visual realm is broadened by including aspects of politics, economic, technology, ecology, climate and religion. According to Isomaa, Korpua, Teittinen (2020) in *New Perspectives on Dystopian Fiction in Literature and Other Media*, writes about the changing nature of dystopian fiction as,

The growing popularity of dystopian fiction is that it seems to have gained cultural independence from its thematically, narratologically, and historically close connection with science fiction and become recognizable in its own right, without reference to sci-fi or speculative fiction as a necessary interpretative frame. This has to do also with the fact that diverse, ancient genres-from religious apocalypse to utopia-come together in contemporary dystopian fiction. (xvi)

Pakistani speculative sci-fi challenges the Western narratives and establishes the distinctive space in the sci-fi by incorporating the ingenious elements. Sheh-e-Tabassum (2020) is lauded by critics for its indigenous aspects. Anmol Irfan applauds Sheh-e-Tabassum's uniqueness and writes, "A newer generation of authors is bringing together their past and present to represent what a South Asian-based sci-fi story can mean to the world." (2021) Pakistani artists are subverting the established authorities of the West in sci-fi, by producing culturally rich dystopian fiction.

Model Citizen, (2020) produced and directed in the West, offers an insight into the past. Although, it is a dystopian fiction, but it re-imagines the present through the past. Olivia Eyeston (2021) writes about the presence of past in the film as, “This film is very fast paced: scenes just fly by one after another, giving the film chaotic energy that definitely fits the plot.” The recurrence of the scenes takes the audience back and forth commenting on the chaos: a distinctive feature of dystopian society.

To resist the oppressive structures in dystopian society, is also usually embedded in the narrative of speculative fiction. Hazel Tan writes, “even though the film seems mundane without plot progression initially, there is a disguise of revolution hidden within the narrative.” Therefore, the elements of resistance have been ingrained in the mundane and gruesome depiction of the society. The review of the literature on dystopia and panopticon reveals multiple roles of such concepts to understand the emerging use of technology in science fiction. Along with technology, the idea of surveillance to decipher the handling of societies through control is developed. The existing writings on Shehr-e-Tabassum (2020) and Model Citizen (2020) are reviewed to establish the research gap. Therefore, this paper is an attempt to understand overlapping themes of erasure of identity in sci-fi animations produced in the East and West.

Theoretical Framework

Michel Foucault’s (1975) Discipline and Punish: The Birth of Prison delivers the idea that panopticon is a strategy which can be used to untangle the power structures. The emanation of power through obscured objects has potential to control human behavior. Considering this, the concept of panopticon becomes prominent for understanding dystopia in Model Citizen and Shehr-e Tabassum. Foucault writes about surveillance as “inspection functions ceaselessly.” (1975, 195) Modern societies are also witnessing the scrutiny of individuals through data base of the states, which incessantly monitor these individuals.

Moreover, application of surveillance through panopticon structures is not just limited to watching; rather, it is headed for disciplining the individuals to “assure the automatic functioning of power.” (1975, 201) Exerting power via panoptic structures originate instinctively; its integration, in the subtlest ways,

ensures the prevalence of anticipated discipline amongst the individuals. The concept of panopticon is employed to understand the powers dynamics in Shehr-e-Tabassum and Model Citizen.

Discussion and Analysis

An ever-increasing advancement in technology has paved way for speculative fiction to emerge as a trend. The twentieth and twenty first centuries have observed a significant production and inclusion of sci-fi across various literary genres. Dystopian fiction and speculative fiction have been blended for a more immersive and notable futuristic experience for the audience. Foucault’s theory of surveillance and control becomes relevant while critically evaluating the plot and setting of such literary pieces. The following section highlights how Mazhar’s Shehr-e-Tabassum and Armsby’s Model Citizen depict a dystopian society, governed primarily by internally regulated control. A comparative analysis between directors from East and West would set the basis for further debate. It traces the universality of power and its misuse for widespread inculcation of dehumanization techniques aimed to achieve so-called peace.

Shehr-e-Tabassum

Mazhar’s Shehr-e-Tabassum mirrors a totalitarian society. It is dominated by the structures of control and power. The visual storytelling in Shehr-e-Tabassum acts as a form of resistance against existing constraints of dystopia which influences individuals both directly and indirectly. Foucault’s idea that “power should be visible and unverifiable” (p.201), is integral in understanding how the gadgets distributed by the government serve as an oppressive tool. It aimed at handicapping the individuals cognitively by targeting their thought process. Submission to the rigid power structures can be observed by the ever-smiling face of individuals. Every good citizen is defined as the one who is always smiling, this is, agreeing with the state policies. “Hasmukh” is a gadget that is mandatory for the citizens to wear. (Mazhar, 2020, 00:43). It ensures that citizens are abiding by the behavioural manual designed by the law enforcement committees. One of the salient traits of dystopian society is to introduce laws. Everyone must abide by certain rules and regulations. In Shehr-e-Tabassum

the citizens are not allowed to remove the gadget, as it will lead to the violation of “Clause 9” (Mazhar, 2020, 00:57) resulting in their punishment. Oppressive rules and regulations in a society grant immense power to its rulers. Resistance is the only tool that may be used to curb enforced and coercive practices.

The citizens in the futuristic world are under continuous surveillance through Hasmukh gadget. The citizens are informed about its expiry and therefore, they are supposed to get a more advanced “Smileton Hassmukh-Premium X-2 5000.” (Mazhar, 2020, 00:53) Implantation of such devices in the individuals is a gateway allowing for identification of the iconoclastic figures. Their categorization will assist domination and efficiency of restriction against non-conformist perspectives. Eventually, it will assist prevalence of cognitive majoritarianism.

Social commentary in the film challenges the normalization of such surveillance techniques at a state level. Constantly several announcements are made in the background, while people are preoccupied with daily chores. Simultaneously, with the verbal announcements, visual presentation makes the audience normalize the existence of unreal contrasted with real. Panopticon of the past replicates to the surveillance practices through technology in futuristic world.

Dystopian world as visually presented to the audience in Shehr-e-Tabassum incorporated mass poverty as well. Daniyal’s parents are worried because of his health as he was unable to smile. They feared that state would confiscate their son as he was not conforming to the norm. On the other hand, Imtiaz is unable to take care of his child, and he was suggested by the shopkeeper to get “points” (Mazhar, 2020, 01:36) from “muskan bank” (Mazhar, 2020, 01:55). Exposition of these two images simultaneously refers to the presence of mass poverty in the short film, as citizens are unable to afford the medicines. State is happy to assist citizen in assisting by providing them with the smileton, while de-voiding citizen from the basic amenities of life. The right to life is compromised in a dystopian world at the cost of state spending solely on oppressive power structures. This also poses a critical inquiry to decipher the rights and obligations of the state and its citizen.

Projection of power in the Shehr-e Tabassum is through a security bot, an alien figure. The dystopian

short film depicts the regularization of alien figures’ presence with humans. It is a satire to observe how the agents of power are the bots. A security bot identifies a non-smiling citizen, and the citizen is put into a detention center. It is a quagmire that humans are not identifying the humans rather a robot is powerful to identify the human being for not abiding the law. Foucault’s panopticon towers have semblance to the presence of the power emanating not through the spy rather through a robot, a characteristic feature of speculative fiction, presented through a security bot in short film (1975, p.200).

Immense power has been given to the security bots in Sher-e-Tabassum. Two citizens in the short film are found having elevated cortisol levels. They are identified and arrested because they have shown a “suspicious behaviour” (Mazhar, 2020, 05:09). Identification by the bots and then arresting by the bots reflect the unverifiable power of the state structures. Interestingly, the resistance does not totally vanish from Shehr-e Tabassum, Mazhar has subtly weaved the elements of resistance in the first part of the short film. An old man is observed coughing and mentions, oppressor is now looking directly into our eyes and is oppressing (Mazhar, 2020, 02:13). Such image in the greater scheme of things in futuristic state hints upon the presence of agents challenging the dominating and controlling narratives. People who do not succumb to the general ideologies rather believe in employing their cognitive abilities to understand the underlining agenda behind the implantation of robotic devices.

Subsequently, a girl in the last part of the film is seen running as if she is hiding from surveillance of the state. The panting sounds are heard, and she is running on the streets to hide herself. Presence of cyborg through the smileton is presented in the film as every citizen is wearing it and citizens are also presented wearing the helmets. Through the helmets the devices are implanted and the girl in the end refuses to wear it (Mazhar, 2020, 07:25). Ultimately, she finds a place and immediately disconnects the device, thus strongly challenging the mass surveillance and totalitarian state apparatus.

Disciplining of the human emotions is also a prevalent theme in animated Shehr-e Tabassum. It is announced that facial expressions other than smile is a crime and anyone not smiling can be reported to the

concerned authorities (Mazhar, 2020, 02:34). Similarly, citizens are not allowed to have facial hair (Mazhar, 2020, 01:16). Such techniques of disciplining belittle the humanism of individuals. Foucault writes about discipline as, "Discipline 'makes' individuals; it is the specific technique of a power that regards individuals as objects" (1975, p.170). Thus, there is a loss of individualism and survival is the only option where human beings are morphed into objects.

In a futuristic state, Mazhar has incorporated the cultural trope of street vendor. Satirical representation of street vendor chanting "get your devices repaired" (Mazhar, 2020,01:17) is presented against the culture of street vendors in Pakistan chanting get your kitchen ware repaired. In a dystopic state the penetration of technology is evident through the chants of street vendors. This also points out the hyper normalization of technological gadgets in every nook and corner of Shehr-e-Tabassum.

Shehr-e-Tabassum has visual presentation of the technology hijacking the normality of cityscapes. Presence of air rickshaw and spaceships in the city reflects how alien objects have been a metaphor of technological advancement dominating the normality of cities. These unusual objects in the city space questions the incorporation of the technology which is terminating the essence of the technological advancement. Such dystopia reflects how the human led advancement is a threat to human survival.

Color scheme in Sher-e-Tabasum captures the attention of the viewer's multiple times. Mazhar has used vibrant colours like dark green, pink, red and blue against the black backdrop. Such scheme of colours represents the emergence of unreal against the real. The popping up of the colours simultaneously directs the attention of the viewer one after another on important aspects, such as use of green colour while mentioning the "Muskan bank" (Mazhar,2020,01:55) in the beginning sets the tone of the short film.

Use of black screen after the detention of Daniyal reflects upon the tragedy that Daniyal was unable to smile. Specifically, the black colour symbolizes the bleak and dark society dominated by the unreal objects and technology. Dystopian societies are bleak societies and are antagonistic to utopian societies. Therefore, use of black backdrop and black colour

again and again directs the attention towards an unhappy society.

Cinematographically, the lightening in the short film through different angles also reflects cataclysmic decline of humanity in the dystopian state. The flashing and intense lights symbolize the warnings of an emergence of an apocalyptic world. It also highlights the emergence of the crisis and amplifies the situation where the security bot specifically targets the citizen and identifies the expression other than smile. Visual representations of such danger using light directed towards different angles etch the images of dark world in the minds of viewers of Shehr-e-Tabassum.

Mazhar has used numerous sounds together in one scene. The use of numerous sounds at one time is emblematic of anarchy in the futuristic state, where technology overpowers everything. Daniyal's state of misery is juxtaposed with "muskan bank" (Mazhar,2020,01:55). Machine's sound and the sirens all reflect upon a situation of crisis, where in totality nothing is making sense. Such sounds in Shehr-e Tabassum amplify the panic created using technology in dystopic state.

The title of the short film Shehr-e Tabassum is ironic in its nature. Speculative fiction shifts the attention of the reader from the reality. Therefore, the title as translated means city of happiness, is a fantastical idea. Such developments of cities are impossible. The major theme of happiness as the only allowed expression for the citizen is also an imaginative realm. These ideas can only be a product of creative imagination where unreal, futuristic and supernatural elements can take precedence over the reality.

Model Citizen

Model Citizen by David James Armsby launched in year 2020, opens with a public service announcement airing the television screen. Re-iteration of social constructs and norms is targeted towards mass audience at nighttime through the announcement. The timing for the notices has been chosen meticulously by the director. The beginning is quite abrupt and makes the audience plunge straight into the narrative. AutoDale is an automated, futuristic town where the citizens are ruled by systematic powers. The system regulated by the robots check and balance is quite rigid in its terms and conditions.

Perfectionism runs through the society with the assistance of robots, who feed manipulative and deceptive tactics to the citizens. Masks are a significant feature in the film as they are used as a tool to cover up reality. Masks facilitate the persona that the citizens must live up to, to be categorized as the perfect, model citizen. The ideal citizen of AutoDale is supposed to be a “providing father; a caring mother” (Armsby, 2020, 0:25-0:29). Acceptance of labels has been drilled in men and women; children are no exception from distinctive roles classified for them by the state. Hence, parents are supposed to ensure that the “perfect cycle never ends” (Armsby, 2020, 01:39).

Implementation of laws and uniform public narrative ensures there is no diversity and individuality in the humans, and they conform to the societal laws and practices. This monotonous and mundane cycle must cease to exist until these citizens fulfill their designated task of performing, conforming and passing down the same values in the generations to come.

Self-regulation is a fundamental aspect of surveillance and control. Panopticon proposes that once the societies have been brainwashed at large, ideally, they need not be probed further to make certain that these individuals are submissive to the prevailing law.

Black and white color scheme employed in the short film heightens the ambience of bleakness overpowering the lives of citizens under consideration. It showcases the stark division of their life rules, in clear cut distinctions of black and white. Inclusion and acceptance of diversified emotions and human experiences in the town or its inhabitants is not permissible. Probability, in-betweenness, shades of grey are not to be tolerated and/or spared. However, towards the end of the film red colour appears quite shockingly. Red is the color of sacrifice, courage and danger, as well as the color of blood. Categorization of black and white against bright red tends to draw a line between obedience and retaliation.

Robinsons are the central characters around whom the story evolves. Their psychological state is pitiable as these humans have lost touch of reality. They have come to terms with the narrative and agenda gushed down their systems. These characters do not have any facial expressions for most part of the film as their faces are covered beneath the masks they have put on.

These masks are a projection of their subjugation and dismissal of their unique perceptions.

Timing in Model Citizen becomes irrelevant as there is a chaotic energy that reverberates through the film. Fast paced as the short film was, it runs parallel to the robotic lifestyle that humans at the town of AutoDale have been reduced to. The plot of the short film has a close comparison with T.S Eliot’s “Hollow Men.” The director seems to be lamenting on the fact, that humans have lost their intrinsic values and sensitivity to fit into systemic regimes. Towards the end, these perfectly performing citizens are lined up, wearing the mask labelled as: “ugly.” (Armsby, 2020, 2:51) The individualism of the central characters, and their merger with the rest of the ominous characters portrays the irony of the system. Once these people offer all they possess to sustain the perfect cycle, they are no longer of any use. Their identification from ‘nameless’ to ‘ugly’ reflects on their acquired hollowness by the end of oppressive cycle.

The director shed light on the impact of control, surveillance and subjugation on societies and ultimately humanity. It must be noticed that the film came out in the year 2020. That is when the world was experiencing a global epidemic, namely: Covid-19. The restrictions and the limitations seeping in daily life regime displays an intense impact on the director. The situation at hand, presented via the short film, is in line with the experiences of being caged. The relatability of the film content at a time which was universally depressing, makes the animation even darker.

The geography of the film set reveals directors motif of world making. Consequently, here the characters are restricted to their household space. The confined space narrows down the possibilities of exposure for the Robinsons’. This produces a certain sense of tension and claustrophobic environment in the short film. The gaze of the audience is constantly in search for further details the director might be utilizing to drop hints for the audience. Towards the end of the film, the Robinsons are seen lined up with the remaining once-perfect citizens to meet their fate. The setting at this point is very similar to that of a concentration camp. These submissive and obedient townspeople had been contained in barbed wires. The limitation of space offered to these characters is a clear-cut reflection of their agency in the premises of

AutoDale. The climax reaches when Joe, the robot, mechanically performs his duty to get rid off the model citizens. While the Robinsons are shown to be expressing raw and untamed emotion by expressing their love, kissing each other and taking their masks off; Joe interrupts with the slogan, "Duty Calls," terminating their life.

Tchaikovsky's "Waltz of the Flowers" plays in the background as the film progresses. This allows deeper inward focus on what is happening on-screen. Audience feels compelled to feel elated with joyous track as the bleakness of the narrative is explored. The choice of music is a deliberate move which urges the audience to critically evaluate what is being shown. The short film reveals the problematic socio-cultural fabric of the modern society. Showcasing these ideas on-screen allows the director to turn the subject matter of the short film accessible to local and global audience. It leaves the audience with a nerve-wrecking rhetorical question: Is there something worse than failing to initiate subversion of societal expectations and inhumanity? The unquestionable and robot-like dance of these citizens on the melodious tunes, deaf to their inner voice and critical thinking skills, offers an ultimatum to the terrifying age where science and technology have begun to take over humanity.

'Shehr-e-Tabasum' and 'Model Citizen,' both short animation films portray the grim yet relatable existence of a dystopian society. Although there are substantial contrasting ideas between the East and the West; however, when it comes to experiencing hazard of dehumanization, they seem to share a mutual sentiment and perspective. Mazhar's characters are forced to conceal their emotional, rational and psychological state with the use of Hasmukh gadget. On the other hand, Armsby's characters are constantly regulated through external pressure for conformity and behaviour monitoring. The Western director is more inclined towards criticising the totalitarian regimes. Whereas Mazhar's primary concern is masked happiness and/or complete submission to authority which leads to erasure of an individual's existence. It presents retaliation to restriction that stops people from expressing their authentic self.

Resistance is one of the key aspects that have been explored by both the directors. Mazhar and Armsby have both identified that there could be some form of

non-conformity in the face of dictatorial societal norms. Even though the film seems mundane without plot progression initially, there is a disguise of revolution hidden within the narrative. (Tan, n.d)

However, there is one major distinction between both animations. Mazhar's short film depicts the tension present in the characters that is heightened as the story progresses. Armsby on the contrary, has not explicitly explored the realm of rebellion. The characters in Model Citizen reflect a fictive society which is overridden by automation. The Robinsons' do not dare defy the system, since, if they do, they will have to meet their destined fate, that is, death. Here, the conflict is not only about meeting a designated punishment if they fail to perform. The problem is that the characters must die once they have completed a certain task which had been assigned to them.

Inability to evade the panopticon system and inescapable dehumanization is an alternative theme that has been revealed in both animations. "Nevertheless, in the past few years, human-robot interactions have raised many ethical concerns, related to our future coexistence with them, as they become more powerful and impactful day by day." (Broadbent, 2017) Foucault's concept of panopticon is deeply intertwined and ingrained within the dystopian society. Computerization, artificial intelligence, robots are all tools for manipulation and controlling of the society at large. East and West both have the same concerns when it comes to seeing their freedom at stake at the hands of those in power.

Control; conformity and resistance; psychological manipulation; visibility and self-regulation are a few elements of panopticon explored in these films. On the contrary, the aspect of dehumanization and surveillance have been clearly highlighted in these short films - reflecting on the downside of an automated, technology driven, futuristic dystopian society.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the invention of societies in Shehr-e-Tabasum and Model Citizen raise serious questions about the use of technology. Both short films are dystopian in nature, emphasizing the adverse consequences of technology driven control and misuse of artificial intelligence. Power in societies is re-enacted through cyborgs. Security bots in Shehr-e-Tabasum are agents of power continuously

monitoring citizen whereas; in Model Citizen the individuals are brainwashed and controlled through various mechanical structures. Depiction of such controlled, totalitarian societies present the need to conduct a critical inquiry. Scholars need to undergo the narratives presented in fictions and work towards their re-contextualization in the larger scheme of technological advances prevalent in the contemporary society. Dystopian fiction produced in both East and West suggest that execution of power through modern surveillance techniques are devoiding societies off the vibrancy and warmth of humanness. The findings of the research have far-reaching implications in a contemporary world. It opens avenues for comparative analysis based on unifying factors between Eastern and Western societies. It compels the audience to foster a greater understanding for humanity and the need for an inclusive society. The research allows the audience to reflect on the irreversible impact of conformity on humanity and re-awaken the critical, rational self.

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